

I-RIM 2025 Workshop proposal

Dynamic Manipulation Based on Artificial Vision and Touch

Workshop Objectives and Main Topics

Human manipulation relies on a combination of dexterous hands, tactile sensing, and visual feedback to maintain controlled interactions with objects, even without a firm grasp, as in the case of a waiter carrying a tray. Recent robotic advances aim to replicate these skills through vision, tactile, and force sensors for both in-hand and whole-body manipulation, including multi-arm coordination. Key control strategies include object tracking, force control, internal force estimation, and non-prehensile manipulation. Robots must modulate grasping forces to handle both rigid and deformable objects without damage. While parallel grippers dominate industrial applications due to their simplicity, recent research demonstrates that even these devices can perform complex tasks using extrinsic dexterity, for example, exploiting gravity to pivot or slide objects within the gripper. In cluttered environments, intrinsic dexterity becomes critical. Direct grasping may be unfeasible, making non-prehensile actions like pushing or sliding more effective to reposition objects. Although more complex, such actions are part of our daily behavior and offer a broader range of manipulation strategies for robots. Visual feedback supports object tracking and grasp planning in both prehensile and non-prehensile scenarios. However, visual sensing can be hindered by occlusions or lighting. Tactile sensing, while requiring contact, provides robust feedback. Combining both modalities can overcome their individual limitations, offering more adaptive and resilient control.

This workshop will highlight cutting-edge research in dynamic manipulation, showcasing results from the DARC consortium and the broader robotics community, with a focus on integrating force/tactile and visual feedback for dexterous robotic tasks. The workshop will cover a wide range of topics related to dynamic manipulation using artificial vision and touch. The key areas include:

- In-hand manipulation strategies
- Non-prehensile manipulation: pushing, sliding, and transporting
- Grasp of deformable and rigid objects
- Tactile sensing: contact and slip detection
- Visual perception: object tracking, pose estimation, and challenges
- Feedback control using tactile and visual data
- Modeling, estimation, and control of multi-arm setups

Keywords: Dynamic and Non-Prehensile Manipulation; Extrinsic Dexterity; Robotic Vision; Perception for Manipulation; Manipulation of Deformable Objects; Multi-arm Manipulation.

Organizers and format

The list of organizers with their affiliation is

- Marco Costanzo (corresponding organizer), Department of Engineering, University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”.
email: marco.costanzo@unicampania.it
- Mario Selvaggio (corresponding organizer), Department of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering, University of Naples Federico II. *email: mario.selvaggio@unina.it*
- Fabio Ruggiero, Department of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering, University of Naples Federico II. *email: fabio.ruggiero@unina.it*
- Ciro Natale, Department of Engineering, University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”. *email: ciro.natale@unicampania.it*

The workshop will feature five invited speakers with a final round table. The format is *invitation-only*.

The workshop duration is 90 minutes. Each invited speaker will have 15 minutes to present their recent research advancements in the field. Afterward, the workshop will end with a round table discussion where the speakers will deepen the discussion around their presentations topics and the audience can ask questions.

Invited Speakers

The list of invited speakers who accepted to deliver a talk to our workshop is

- Lorenzo Natale ^{*TBC}; Italian Institute of Technology. Title of the talk: “Domain adaptation for learning tactile object features with vision-based sensors”
- Alessandro Marino, Department of Electrical and Information Engineering “Maurizio Scarano”, Università degli Studi di Cassino e del Lazio Meridionale. Title of the talk: “Coordinated multi-arm control for manipulation in complex settings”
- Alessio Caporali ^{*TBC}, Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell’Energia Elettrica e dell’Informazione “Guglielmo Marconi”, Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna. Title of the talk: “Model-based Tracking of Deformable Linear Objects in Challenging Environments”
- Alessandro Saccon ^{*TBC}, Mechanical Engineering Department, Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e). Title of the talk: “**TBC**”
- Maria Pozzi; Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell’Informazione e Scienze Matematiche, Università di Siena. Title of the talk: “Soft manipulation: the role of mechanical intelligence in robotic grasping”

Note on the preferred date: the speakers indicated with ^{*TBC} will be available only if the workshop takes place on the first day 17/10/2025. Therefore, we indicate such a date as our preferred date.

Notes on registration: we will offer the two one-day registrations to two speakers, to be selected in agreement with all five speakers.

Expected audience and outcomes

Given the expertise of the speakers, we anticipate that the workshop will be targeted to young PhD students and researchers working in the broad field of dynamic manipulation and robot vision and touch. Based on our previous experience on the organization of an I-RIM workshop, we expect to host approximately 20 to 30 people.

The organizers are preparing a special issue proposal to RA-L or T-RO on the main topics of this workshop. We will invite speakers and attendees to publish their work announcing the special issue at the end of the workshop.

Further information can be found at the workshop website
<https://sites.google.com/view/i-rim-2025-workshop-darc>